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Linguistic Identity of a Teacher of Federal and Departmental Higher Educational Establishments of the Russian Federation: General and Special Issues

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Abstract

The relevance of the article is due to the fact that one of the main current educational directions defining humanist culture of a personality is a sound grasp of a language of the personality. This requires identifying new ways to the content of education that consists in preparing a new generation of teachers who would work well within economic and social digitization, ethnical and sociocultural diversity. The goal of the study is to identify specifics of linguistic identity of the teacher of federal and departmental higher educational establishments of the Russian Federation located in Kazan. We assume that specifics of linguistic identity influences on the ability of the teacher to present training material, besides a type of educational organization shape the teacher's personality. The Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan (Volga region) Federal University teachers and students and the Kazan Law Institute of MIA of Russia teachers, cadets and students took part in the study. Factorial qualitative analysis of in-depth interviews of the student body, questionnaires were used as empirical methods. The article presents several examples of linguistic identities of the teachers from each the educational establishments and some observations about them. The materials presented in the article allow to draw conclusion: linguistic identity formation lasts during the whole life, thus self-education of the personality within the field should not only focus on school or including when a person depending on the type of his/her professional activity should be a role model for his/her subordinated.

Keywords: linguistic personality, elite linguistic personality, professional linguistic personality, teacher.

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Introduction

Consequently, the problem of developing readiness of deviant behavior-prone adolescents for family life, besides being relevant, is also of great social significance. One of the main directions of the modern concept of education, which defines the humanistic culture of the individual, is a confident command of the language.

The phenomenon of linguistic personality (hereinafter LP), introduced into the scientific circulation by Bogin (1984) and studied later by Karaulov (2014), for some time belonged only to philologists and linguists. Despite the fact that this concept appeared for the first time in the works of Weisgerber (2004) and Vinogradov (1980), in the 20-30s of the XX century, they did not give an accessible and scientific definition of it.

During the 40 years of the existence of this concept in the science, its study has taken place in various aspects: there were attempts to study “linguistic-cultural types”, from the British Queen to a school teacher; scientists studied the linguistic personality in the language (on the works of foreign and domestic writers and poets); there were experiments to make a speech portrait of representatives of different strata of the population, rank, sex and place of residence; a non-normative vocabulary in the light of the concept of the linguistic personality was studied, and there were presented a number of studies.

A little later, teachers and psychologists also began to use this concept in their study: they studied the linguistic personality of translators and future teachers; linked the linguistic personality and communicative behavior; studied the emotional behavior of LP, etc.

However, in the study of LP, in our view, the studies devoted to revealing the relationship between LP and its self-identification through the prism of ethnic, confessional and national environment have taken a special place in the domestic science. First of all, it is caused by the multinational aspect of the Russian Federation. The majority of such studies are devoted to the study of children, teenagers, and adults in a polylingual environment.

The Republic of Tatarstan is the very subject of the Russian Federation where the main confessions (Orthodoxy and Islam) are intertwined, the two largest ethnic groups (Russians and Tatars) are concentrated and, as a result, there is a natural bilingual (polylingual) environment fixed at the state level.

Purpose and objectives of the study

The goal of the study is to identify specifics of linguistic identity of the teacher of federal and departmental higher educational establishments of the Russian Federation located in Kazan.

Literature review

Speaking about the linguistic personality, Karaulov (2014) noted that it is impossible to learn a language without going beyond its limits, without addressing its creator, carrier, user – a person, a specific LP.

However, as noted by all scientists who have addressed the LP, there are no universal and clearly defined criteria for the formation of LP in any science (linguistics, psychology, pedagogy). Solving this issue, researchers often resort to describing a specific LP, observation and analysis of the linguistic characteristics of this LP. As a result, each scientist dealing with the issue of LP obtains a certain set of specific features of the linguistic characteristics of any individual person.

Thus, Kochetkova (1998, pp. 94-101), considering the outstanding LP of a particular “carrier of an elitist speech culture”, notes as typological factors of LP, first of all: the family (cultural environment, parents that are fond of reading, early inculcation of reading skills, the presence of a home library); intellect (“Elitarness always implies a high intellect, reasonableness of a person... The mental activity of such a person is active the whole life. The level of a person’s thinking depends to a great extent on natural intellect”, p. 94); great love for books (scientific, fiction, journalistic); acquaintance with the best samples of Russian poetry; constant, which has become natural, reference and dictionary literature on various occasions, daily reading of newspapers; magazine publications control); good knowledge of foreign languages, which allows reading non-translated literature; good education and continuous self-education. The carrier of an elitist speech culture has such values as respect for people, law, order, business, profession, i.e. a strongly developed sense of universal respect and a sense of social responsibility. Such a person very often puts the sign of equality between the chosen profession and the favorite thing”).

According to the figurative expression of Kochetkova (1998, p. 20), “the interests of all sciences converge in personality”. Developing the idea of the scientist, we can add “linguistic” before the word “personality”, since the concept of “linguistic personality”, which puzzled some scientists a few decades ago, today has rightfully come into the usage of specialists in various scientific disciplines: linguistics, pedagogy, psychology, literature, as well as related disciplines, which study human and the texts generated by him.

A famous Russian scientist Karaulov (2014), the author of fundamental studies in the field of the theory of linguistic personality, noted that he saw no obstacles to the application of his developed “generic” model of linguistic personality, which consisted of three intersecting axes – “types of speech activity” (speaking, listening, writing, reading), “levels of language” (phonetics, grammar, vocabulary) and “the degree of possession of the relevant components of this level”, as a reference-analyser that diagnoses the state of linguistic development of a particular individual.

Thus, the promotion of the linguistic personality as a strategic reference point of educational policy is dictated by both the essence of this phenomenon and the status of speech development of the personality as the basis of any education, argues Shashlova (2006). Considering LP as a universal category, she notes its potential opportunity to have access to such qualities of an individual’s personality as emancipation, creativity, independence, ability to build interaction and mutual understanding with partners in communication (social interaction), to be included in modern world processes of civilization development, to improve human society, which is especially important in the future police officer training in a departmental university.

Methodology

Our study is devoted to defining the features of LP of a teacher at two higher education institutions (federal and departmental) located in Kazan. We assume that the peculiarities of a teacher’s LP have an impact on his/her ability to present educational material; moreover, the specifics of an educational organization also have an impact on the teacher. Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan (Volga region) Federal University teachers and students, as well as the Kazan Law Institute of the Russian Ministry of Internal Affairs teachers and cadets and students took part in the study.

The educational activities of the Institute of Psychology and Education are aimed at training a qualified specialist in the field of education, a socially mature person with a high level of civic and social activity, a person capable of effective adaptation and life activity in a dynamically changing society, a person who is active and able to find an effective balance between individual, group, corporate and public interests.

The peculiarity and specificity of educational activity in a departmental higher education institution is, first of all, its closeness due to restrictions imposed by the Federal laws “On police”, “On service in the internal affairs bodies of the Russian Federation” and others. Nevertheless, a future specialist – an employee of the internal affairs agencies or a graduate of a departmental educational institution qualified as a lawyer – should realize the importance of developing business communication skills and improving the level of speech culture in his/her professional activity. In this regard, new approaches to higher education, and

departmental, including the search for innovative teaching methods, actualize the interest in the communicative and developing potential of educational disciplines. The image then prevalent in the public consciousness for a long time (not without the participation of the mass media and television, which massively replicated the image of a rough “mentality”) of a law enforcement officer as a poorly educated person, poorly versed in both the oral and written Russian language, with a low cultural level, fortunately, in the past. In the opinion of our colleagues, “the professional training of future specialists in the field of law enforcement, based on its main goals and objectives, should be moral standing, since law enforcement itself is initially imbued with morality and ethics” (Eroshenkov, 2014, p. 25).

Formation of a personality of a future law enforcement officer implies not only laying the fundamental foundations of this personality’s culture: the culture of self-determination in life, culture of communication, economic, intellectual, political (democratic), legal, ecological, physical, artistic, and labor culture (Grishinov et al., 2017), but also the creation of conditions for professional thinking, culture of professional communication (Ogorodnik & Igonin, 2015). And here we will express solidarity with Khabarin (2018), who proposes to include professional speech culture in the concept of “professionalism”.

In light of this, it is necessary to define new approaches to the content of education, which consists in training teachers of new generation, effectively working in the conditions of digitalization of economy and society, ethnic and socio-cultural diversity. In view of these requirements, it is essential and interesting to address the teacher’s LP research.

Taking the scheme proposed by Kochetkova (1998) as a basis, we have prepared a questionnaire allowing to characterize the teacher’s LP and suggested the students (cadets) to analyze the personality of a particular teacher (commander).

Questionnaire for trainees:

1. Is there a teacher about whom you would say that this is an elite LP?
2. What factors have influenced the formation of the teacher’s personality? (Family, cultural environment, love of reading and home library, education, etc.).
3. What is the continuous self-education of this person (in science, general development, hobbies, etc.)?
4. What languages the teacher speaks? (Native, foreign).

5. Is it possible to say that the teaching activity gives him/her satisfaction?
6. Indicate the speech, extra-linguistic and paralinguistic peculiarities of the teacher's communication.

In total 150 students (full-time and part-time) of the Institute of Psychology and Education of Kazan Federal University (hereinafter KFU) and 150 cadets of the Kazan Law Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia took part in the study. The study was conducted from September to December 2019.

The students were asked to address the personalities of their contemporaries to their university professors. The results of the survey allowed us to identify several representatives of the faculty of the two universities, who received the maximum number of responses from the respondents. These professors have become the object of our further study.

In addition to the questionnaire, we conducted interviews with the students, who noted these teachers. We were also interested in the styles, forms of communication between teachers and students, students and cadets in the academic and extracurricular periods.

Results

The material for observation were oral speech (lectures and seminar sessions, direct communication of students with the teacher, his/her communication in scientific circles, with colleagues, household communication) and written speech (digital or electronic educational resources (digital learning resources and electronic learning resource in KFU), electronic information educational environment (Electronic Information Educational System in Kazan Law Institute of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Russia), published lectures, articles and speeches at conferences, comments on term papers, graduation works of students and cadets, students, reviews, etc.). In addition, some teachers of the federal university actively use Internet resources for communication with students (professional websites of educators, the possibility of using social networks: VKontakte, Odnoklassniki, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, etc.), sending them for additional materials to their sites. Some teachers run their own blogs (it was taken into account that in their turn, in a departmental university, access to social networks is restricted).

As a result of the study, students noted the following typological features of a civil and departmental university teacher's LP which, in their opinion, are the most attractive and respected.

Description of a teacher's LP of the Institute of Psychology and Education of KFU

We would like to note the fact that during the processing of questionnaires and interviews, the students of the Institute of Psychology and Education described mainly male teachers (they are several times fewer than female teachers). We can explain this by the fact that 95% of female students and only 5% of male students participated in the survey. We cited some of the respondents' opinions.

P 1. "Intellectual"

All students noted that he is a person who speaks literary language: "I have learned many words only after attending his lectures, he expands my vocabulary", "I started using the words he uses".

The personality is versatile and creative: "He writes artistic poetry and prose", "He is engaged in painting, his wonderful paintings should be in the art gallery".

One of the main characteristics of the LP "Intellectual", noted by the participants of the experiment in describing this teacher, is a sense of humor: "At first, I did not understand that he was joking, because in some cases when he joked, he looked quite serious. I think that if he had a mustache, it would help him hide a smile in his mustache", "I always wait for his comments on an event at lectures", "His lectures can be listened to for hours, and his jokes help us memorize the material".

He is always extremely polite to everyone: "Even when he says "hello" to me, he calls me by my name, but he has so many students", "When he meets me, he nods to me along with the greeting".

Extensive reading: "I am sometimes afraid to imagine how many books he has read", "He has knowledge in almost all fields – he can tell so much about anything you ask".

Authority among colleagues: "Colleagues always speak about him only positive words", "Some teachers even quote him".

P 2. "The dream of all the girls at the institute"

Highly methodical training: "Do you have any idea how much I have to study, look through and read, and then tell him about it to earn his praise, "Oh, good for you!" (his highest grade of student knowledge). I think everybody wants to get that grade, "students always come to school prepared".

Knowledge of several languages: "I learned by chance about the fact that he speaks several languages, and at a fairly confident level – he began reciting poems in their original language", "I heard him talking to

foreigners in their native language, in English, and French, and Italian”, “I’m glad that I can talk to him in Tatar”.

The democratic style of leading an audience: “I’m not afraid to express my opinion in his classes, even if it doesn't coincide with his opinion”, “I’m not afraid to pass him an exam or a pass/fail test”.

Attention to older teachers, care for subordinates, respect for women (staff): “I sometimes watch as his colleagues consult with him on various issues”, “Most girls in our institute secretly in love with him”.

Continuous self-education: “I follow his numerous publications in scientific journals”, “When I read his scientific works, I find each time something new for myself”.

As the results of the tasks, cadets and students respect teachers with a high level of professional knowledge, significant pedagogical and command experience, skillfully combining high demand for themselves and students. It is quite understandable that cadets and trainees feel the need for reasonable imitation and with dignity copy the behavior of their commanders and teachers.

Description of LP of a commander from the Kazan Law Institute of MIA of Russia

K1. “Nordic type”

The former military. His military style is seen both in his appearance (“always tightened”, “the uniform fits him perfectly, the military uniform does not become anybody but him”), and in speech (“speaks clearly, loudly, everything is clear at once, there is no need to ask again”, “having heard the commander’s voice K1, all – both officers and cadets – come to attention”).

Psychologically stable, able to take responsibility for himself and quickly make the best decisions in difficult situations on service (“I watched his behavior in a critical situation – he was the first who reacted to a cadet fainted on stage, organized the provision of assistance, without fuss, clearly”, “I cannot imagine what could throw off his balance, even when he is upset, angry, cadets do not see it”).

A creative person, constantly raises the level of his skills, enjoys confidence as a commander: people address him in a difficult life situation (“His discipline, exactingness to all without exception will not leave anyone indifferent. Even if someone is afraid of him, he still respects him”, “When we learned that he would soon leave the service, some cadets even cried”).

Service in internal affairs bodies is personally significant for K1: “With his attitude to service, he made us realize that our choice of profession was correct”, “When we were at work practice this year, our employees – our former graduates – first of all asked whether K1 was still in service”, “My older brother, also a graduate of our institute, with gratitude and respect recalls K1”.

He is an example for his subordinates: “When the group said that my manner of speaking was similar to that of K1, it was a pleasant surprise for me”, “All his remarks are taken correctly, even if it is not pleasant to hear”.

K2. “A role model”

Appealing to authoritative personalities (his favorite technique in the design of speeches - quoting): “He has ideals that he follows and which he often uses in his speech”, “I mark for myself the words in his speeches. I think I will use them in my speech”).

Respect for women (employees, workers, cadets) (“In our institute, men prevail, but I can note that K2 attitude to women is respectful and attentive”, “I take his behavior towards women as a model”).

Creative personality: “This is a person with a sense of beauty, and he also brings it up in us”, “There are talented cadets in our group and thanks to K2 there always conditions for the development of their talents”.

Attention to veterans, the elderly, care for subordinates and the preservation of traditions of the institute: “When we have holidays at the institute, former employees, veterans are always invited to the celebration and honored”, “I noticed that attitude to previous leaders is always reverent in our institute”, “When he talks about the success of our university, he does not forget to mention those who stood at the origins of the institute”.

His knowledge of languages (“Speaking to us, he often uses Tatar proverbs and sayings as an example, and then necessarily translates into Russian, I’m very pleased with this”, “I am from the region of the republic, where the Tatar language is mostly spoken, and when K 2 uses Tatar words, it's like I am home again”).

Continuing self-study (thesis dissertation, numerous publications in scientific journals): “When he spoke to us at a scientific conference, he wished us not to waste time and to take advantage of the opportunities offered to raise the research level”, “He always encourages and supports those who are engaged in research work”.

I want to be like him (“I remember my father, he was an internal affairs bodies officer, but died early, badly, I was raised by my mother and grandmother, so K2 is an example of what a man should be like first of all and a police officer”, “His uniform fits him very well”).

Good memory (“Even though he is a leader, he remembers all cadets and trainees well”).

Discussions

The results of the conducted study allow to find many points of contact in LP of teachers of the above-mentioned higher education institutions: it is a literate and correct speech, expressiveness of speech, appropriate pauses and logical accents. His/her timbre is calm, soft, musical, “he/she never raises his/her voice”, “his/her voice does not irritate, but it does not lull”, “there are no annoying parasitic filler word in speech”, clear reading, erudition, intelligence, knowledge of several languages (from three to seven), utmost politeness, continuous self-education, high methodological training.

However, the specifics of the fact that a departmental higher education institution is subordinate not only to the Ministry of Science and Higher Education, but also to the Ministry of Internal Affairs impose its own imprint on the PL teacher of the Kazan Law Institute, which is manifested in restraint, strict discipline and observance of subordination.

Conclusion

Thus, the study of the issue led to the following conclusions:

1. It is always important to remember that only a teacher who is an elitist LP is capable of educating another elitist personality.
2. Since the formation of the highest level of LP occurs throughout the life of the individual, in this regard, the work on the formation of LP should not be limited to the walls of school, university, especially in cases where a person by the nature of his/her professional activities must be an elitist LP.
3. The formation of a linguistic personality is possible only in the atmosphere of creative freedom, creative activity. It is through creativity that a person is able to become free and realize his/her potential. Following the above conditions will promote the disclosure of a person’s creative potential, and thus the formation of a linguistic personality.

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